

Keynote lecture

Oxy-fuel combustion capture in selected industrial and gas power processes

IFRF ToTeM 52: Oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS – 27-28 May 2026, Essen (DE)

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Outline

- Introduction on CCS status
- General principles of oxy-fuel combustion capture
 - Overall process description
 - O₂ production
 - CO₂ Compression and Purification Unit (CPU)
 - Oxy-combustion
- Oxy-fuel Capture in Selected Sectors
 - Oxy-fuel capture in the Waste-to-Energy sector
 - Oxy-fuel in other sectors
- Conclusions

Introduction CCS is happening ...

Northern Lights: Europe's First Full-Scale CCS Infrastructure

- Owned equally by TotalEnergies, Equinor and Shell
- Part of Norway's Longship programme for building a complete CCS value chain

Northern Lights: Europe's First Full-Scale CCS Infrastructure

- **Phase 1** (operational since 2025):
 - Capacity: 1.5 Mt CO₂/year. Fully booked by customers
 - Receiving terminal at Øygarden, western Norway
 - CO₂ stored 2,600 m below seabed
 - First CO₂ from Heidelberg Materials cement plant in Brevik
- **Phase 2** (FID March 2025, operational ~2028):
 - Investment: NOK 7.5 billion
 - Capacity expanded to > 5 Mt CO₂/year
 - Customers: Yara (Netherlands), Ørsted (Denmark), Stockholm Exergi (Sweden), Celsio (Norway)
- **Business model:** open-access CO₂ transport and storage as a service
- Cross-border CO₂ transport regulated under the London Protocol

INNOVATION FUND

Deploying innovative net-zero technologies for climate neutrality

Funded by the EU
Emissions Trading System

CO2 capture projects

	Number of projects	Mt CO ₂ /yr (est.)
All capture tech.	29	21
With oxy-fuel tech.	7 (24%)	5.5 (26%)

↳ All in cement sector

CCS role in climate targets

- IEA Net Zero Emissions Scenario requires:
 - ~1 Gt CO₂/year captured by 2030
 - ~7.6 Gt CO₂/year captured by 2050
- CCS must scale by 20 by 2030 to meet targets

	2024 report	2025 report
Operational	50	77 (+54%)
Under construction	44	47
In development	~534	610
Total pipeline capacity	416 Mtpa	513 Mtpa

Source: Global status of CCS Report. The Global CCS Institute.

Capacity of current and planned large-scale CO₂ capture projects vs. the Net Zero Scenario, 2020-2030

[Open](#)

Source: International Energy Agency (IEA) CCUS Projects Database 2024.

General principles of oxy-fuel combustion capture

Oxy-fuel capture process

Oxy-fuel combustion history

- Oxy-fuel used for decades in industry to increase furnace temperature (glass, steel)
- First proposed for EOR in 80's: Horne & Steinberg (1981), Abraham et al. (1982)
- Milestone projects:

- **Schwarze Pumpe** 30 MWth (Vattenfall, 2008–2014) *Source: Monne J., The Lacq Pilot, Period 2006-2013 (2015) Total Report*
- **Lacq project** 30 MWth (TotalEnergies, 2006-2013)

Oxy-fuel capture process

- Key differences with post-combustion solvent capture:
 - No (thermal) energy-intensive regeneration step, but higher electricity demand
 - Lower separation efficiency penalty
 - Mostly CO₂ compression
 - Lower flue gas volume
 - Integrated in the process

Oxygen production

Oxygen production

- For a 500 MWe coal power plant: ca.10,000 t O₂/day required
- Cryogenic distillation: the workhorse of oxygen production

	Economic scale, tonne/day
Cryogenic distillation	< 5,000
Adsorption	< 350
Membrane (polymer)	< 20
Membrane (ITM)	small
Thermochemical	small
Electrochemical	Small

Source: A. Dardea et al. Air separation and flue gas compression and purification units for oxy-coal combustion systems. *Energy Procedia* 1 (2009) 527–534

Oxygen production

- The largest energy penalty for oxy-fuel capture technology
- Potential breakthrough from market rather than technology:
 - O₂ as a by-product of green H₂ production
- The strategic goal of the EU Hydrogen Strategy (Green Deal) is 40 GW installed capacity of renewable hydrogen electrolyzers by 2030:
 - ca. 15 coal power plants

CO₂ Compression and Purification Unit (CPU)

CO₂ Quality Specifications

- CO₂ must meet strict purity requirements for:
 - **ship transport:** Liquid phase, 15 bar, -30-50°C
 - **pipeline transport:** 100 – 150 bar, ambient temperature
- Non-condensable gases
- H₂O, SO₂, NOx: risk of corrosion

Liquid CO ₂ (LCO ₂) Quality Specifications		
Component	Unit	Limit for CO ₂ Cargo within Reference Conditions ¹
Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂)	mol-%	Balance (Minimum 99.81%)
Water (H ₂ O)	ppm-mol	≤ 30
Oxygen (O ₂)	ppm-mol	≤ 10
Sulphur Oxides (SO ₂)	ppm-mol	≤ 10
Nitrogen Oxides (NOx)	ppm-mol	≤ 1.5
Hydrogen Sulphide (H ₂ S)	ppm-mol	≤ 9
Amine	ppm-mol	≤ 10
Ammonia (NH ₃)	ppm-mol	≤ 10
Formaldehyde (CH ₂ O)	ppm-mol	≤ 20
Acetaldehyde (CH ₃ CHO)	ppm-mol	≤ 20
Mercury (Hg)	ppm-mol	≤ 0.0003
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	ppm-mol	≤ 100
Hydrogen (H ₂)	ppm-mol	≤ 50
Cadmium (Cd), Thallium (Tl)	ppm-mol	Sum ≤ 0.03
Methane (CH ₄)	ppm-mol	≤ 100
Nitrogen (N ₂)	ppm-mol	≤ 50
Argon (Ar)	ppm-mol	≤ 100
Methanol (CH ₃ OH)	ppm-mol	≤ 30
Ethanol (C ₂ H ₅ OH)	ppm-mol	≤ 1
Total Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) ²	ppm-mol	≤ 10
Mono-Ethylene Glycol (MEG)	ppm-mol	≤ 0.005
Tri-Ethylene Glycol (TEG)	ppm-mol	Not allowed
BTEX ³	ppm-mol	≤ 0.5
Ethylene (C ₂ H ₂)	ppm-mol	≤ 0.5
Hydrogen Cyanide (HCN)	ppm-mol	≤ 100
Aliphatic Hydrocarbons (C ₃ +) ⁴	ppm-mol	≤ 1,100
Ethane (C ₂ H ₆)	ppm-mol	≤ 75
Solids, particles, dust	Micro-meter (µm)	≤ 1

Original CO₂ spec
 Clarification from original CO₂ spec

Updated component

Updated component

Moved to solids

New component

CO₂ CPU

- CPU is a low temperature separation (flash), composed of one or several stages of:
 - Compression
 - Cooling with refrigeration cycles
 - (Distillation column for high purity)

Source: Spero C. and Yamada T., Callide Oxyfuel Project. Final Results, 2018

CO₂ CPU

- Sources of impurities in oxy-fuel combustion:
 - Air leakage in furnace section
 - Excess O₂ from combustion
 - O₂ purity from ASU
 - Combustion process: H₂O, CO, HCl, HF, NO_x and SO_x
 - Fuel: Ash, Hg, particles, ...
- Typical CO₂ capture rate with CPU: 85-95 %

Oxy-fuel combustion

Oxy-fuel combustion: CO₂ vs. N₂

- Flame speed – Stability and dynamics

Source: Saanum I., Ditaranto M. Experimental Study of Oxy-fuel Combustion under Gas Turbine Conditions, Energy and Fuels (2017) 31:4445. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.6b03114>

Source: Ditaranto, M., Hals J. Effect of Oxy-Fuel Combustion on Instabilities in a Sudden Expansion Combustor. Combustion&Flame (2006) 146:493-512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2006.04.015>

Oxy-fuel combustion

- Kinetics and emissions
 - Close to stoichiometric combustion
 - CO burn out ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{OH}$)
 - Solid carbon ($\text{C} + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$)
 - NOx generally decreased
 - SOx depends on %O₂
 - Soot inhibited
 - Ash, fouling, corrosion,...
- Reduced volume of flue gas
 - Pollutants concentration increase, not necessarily in mass per unit energy

Figure 7. CO emissions versus excess O₂ (EXO) at O₂C = 34% for the 1 bar case and O₂C = 27–30% for the 10 bar case.

Source: Saanum I., Ditaranto M. Experimental Study of Oxy-fuel Combustion under Gas Turbine Conditions, Energy and Fuels (2017) 31:4445. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.6b03114>

Source: Wigley et al, ICL, E.On, OCC1, 2009

Oxy-fuel combustion: CO₂ vs. N₂

- Heat transfer
 - Gas emissivity
 - Higher local flame temperature
 - Radiative heat transfer increased

Source: Ditaranto M., Oppelt T. Radiative heat flux characteristics of methane flames in oxy-fuel atmospheres, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science* (2011) 35:1343-1350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.expthermflusci.2011.05.002>

Oxy-fuel capture in selected sectors

Oxy-fuel combustion: applicable sectors

- Power generation
 - Coal-fired (most developed)
 - Natural gas power generation (GT cycles)
- Cement and Lime production
- Iron and steel
- Glass and metal melting furnaces
- Waste-to-Energy incineration

Source: CEMCAP project. SINTEF Energi, Horizon 2020 Grant 641185

Fig. 2. Progressive development of oxygen blast furnace to energy saving.

Source: Takahashi et al, *SIJ Int.* 55 (2015):1866–1875

Oxy-fuel combustion in the Waste-to-Energy sector

Oxy-fuel combustion in Waste-to-Energy

Source: Fu et al. Conceptual design and process assessment of a MSW waste-to-energy plant with oxy-combustion CO₂ capture, Carbon Management (2025) 16:2473913 <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2025.2473913>

Oxy-fuel combustion of MSW ROFEA test facility at USTUTT

Effect of oxygen distribution on fuel conversion and burn-out

Haraldrud WtE plant (Oslo/NO)

Source: CAPEWASTE project. SINTEF Energi, RCN Grant 281869

Oxy-fuel combustion in Waste-to-Energy

- Carbon negative emissions of 510 kg CO₂/t_MSW can be achieved at the Haraldrud plant
- Capture power consumption is dominated by ASU (53%) and CPU (42%)
- Air leakage is damaging

(b) Specific power consumption of CPU and total value

Source: Fu et al. Conceptual design and process assessment of a MSW waste-to-energy plant with oxy-combustion CO₂ capture, Carbon Management (2025) 16:2473913 <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2025.2473913>

Oxy-fuel combustion in Waste-to-Energy

Optimization of power consumption in priority:

1. minimize furnace air leakage,
2. oxygen excess,
3. oxygen purity

(c) Total specific power consumption

Source: Fu et al. Conceptual design and process assessment of a MSW waste-to-energy plant with oxy-combustion CO₂ capture, Carbon Management (2025) 16:2473913 <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2025.2473913>

Oxy-fuel combustion in Waste-to-Energy

- Oxy-fuel vs. post-combustion comparison

Table 12. Performance comparison results including SPECCA.

	Air-fired without CO ₂ capture	Oxy-combustion	MEA capture
SPECCA, MJ _{LHV} /kgCO ₂	/	2.73	7.80

- Is the comparison fair?

Source: Fu et al. Conceptual design and process assessment of a MSW waste-to-energy plant with oxy-combustion CO₂ capture, Carbon Management (2025) 16:2473913 <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2025.2473913>

Oxy-fuel combustion in Refinery

- Fluid Catalytic Cracker: largest single point emitter of a refinery
- Relatively CO₂-rich flue gas: attractive for oxy-fuel retrofit
- Process strategies:
 - maintain heat balance of the regenerator
 - maintain volumetric flow rate through the bed
 - Impact on dense phase temperature, catalyst-to-oil ratio, and product yields
- Lower CO₂ avoidance cost than post-combustion
 - Despite higher investment cost
 - The net cost advantage comes from the energy side

Oxy-fuel combustion in the gas power generation sector

Allam Supercritical CO₂ Cycle

95% m CO₂
5% m O₂

300 bar
1150 C TIT

Source: Oxy-combustion turbine power plants.IEAGHG report, 2015

Cycle	Turbomachines	Combustion system	Heat exchangers	Oxygen production	Cycle efficiency, %
SCOC-CC	Compressor: 1 Turbine: 2	GT combustor: 1	HRSG: 1	ASU: 1	45-48
MATIANT	Compressors: 1 HP turbine: 2 MP turbine: 2 LP turbine: 2	MP combustor: 1 LP combustor: 1	Regenerator: 2	ASU: 1	40-49
E-MATIANT	Compressors: 1 Turbine: 2	Combustor: 1	Regenerator: 2	ASU: 1	46-47
NET Power	Compressors: 1 Turbine: 3	Combustor: 2	Regenerator: 2	ASU: 1	55-59
Graz cycle	Compressors: 2 HT turbine: 2 HP turbine: 1 LP turbine: 1	Combustor: 1	HRSG: 1 Condenser/ Evaporator: 1	ASU: 1	49-54
CES cycle	HP turbine: 1 HT turbine: 2 LT turbine: 1	Gas generator: 2 Reheater: 1	HRSG: 1	ASU: 1	45-50
AZEP	Compressor: 1 Turbine: 1	Combustor: 1	HT heat exchangers: 3 HRSG: 1	OTM: 4	49-53
ZEITMOP	Air compressor: 1 N ₂ turbine: 1 CO ₂ compressors: 1 HP CO ₂ turbine: 2 LP CO ₂ turbine: 2	Combustor: 2	Air heater: 2 HP CO ₂ heater: 2	OTM: 4	46-51

Conclusions

- CCS is happening at scale
- Oxy-fuel combustion is a promising CCS route
- Oxygen production is the main energy consumer
 - synergy with H₂ prod.?
- CO₂/O₂ atmosphere fundamentally alters all combustion properties
 - but often for the better (smaller furnace, lower NO_x, ...)
- Air leakage is the dominant impurity source

